

HIRSHFELD SURFACE ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEX FORMED BY Cu (II) NITRATE WITH 1-ETHYL-2- (ETHYLTHIO) -1H-BENZO[d]IMIDAZOLE

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The relevance of the research: Hirshfeld surface analysis is a method that enables a more analytical study of intermolecular interactions. This analytical technique allows for the investigation and visualization of the size, shape, quality, and quantity of intermolecular contact surfaces in molecular crystals.

The purpose of the research: [Cu(L)₂(NO₃)₂] kompleks birikma tarkibidagi molekulararo o'zaro ta'sirlarni va ikki o'lchovli barmoq izlari maydonlarini vizuallashtirish maqsadida Crystal Explorer 17,5 dasturi yordamida Xirshfeld yuzasini tahlil qilish.

Methods and techniques: Study of Hirshfeld surface analysis.

Results: The d_{norm} (Figure 1) for the [Cu(L)₂(NO₃)₂] complex molecule was calculated using standard high surface precision.

Figure 1. Hirshfeld surface according to d_{norm} (a) and two-dimensional fingerprint plots (b) showing the percentage contributions of all interactions for the [Cu(L)₂(NO₃)₂] complex

Analysis of two-dimensional fingerprint region plots reveals that the interactions H...H (43.0%), C...H/H...C (13.3%), and O...H/H...O (29.7%) make the greatest contribution to the Hirshfeld surface. The largest portion of the total surface area is occupied by H...H interactions, which result from the interaction between hydrogen atoms in the benzene ring and the methyl group. The greatest contribution of the O...H/H...O effect is explained by the abundance of intermolecular and intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Also, the contribution of the effects of N...C/C...N (1.0%) and C...C/C...C (3.0%) shows a smaller share. This ensures easy and quick comprehension of intermolecular interactions in Hirshfeld surface analysis.

Figure 2. Interaction distances of individual atoms in the crystal structure of the [Cu(L)₂(NO₃)₂] complex (two-dimensional fingerprint areas and their relative ratio at the Hirshfeld surface)

Conclusion: To calculate the Hirshfeld surface, SIF files were processed in the Crystal Explorer 17.5 program to view intermolecular interactions in complex compounds. Expected bright

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red spots near atoms participating in hydrogen bonds according to d_{norm} are shown on the Hirschfeld surface. Fingerprint drawings show the ratio of various interactions (types of hydrogen bonds) on the surface.